

Research

Cooperative Path Planning for Autonomous Robots: A Software Application

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Abstract: Cooperative path planning for autonomous robots is a vital study domain that aims to facilitate the coordinated navigation of several robots through intricate environments, ensuring collision avoidance and job optimization. This study examines the present status of cooperative path planning, emphasizing essential algorithms, communication methodologies, and applications. We offer a framework that amalgamates decentralized communication with real-time path optimization to augment efficiency and safety in multi-robot systems. We also present a simulation demonstrating the proposed methods. We explore a variety of path planning algorithms, including graph search methodologies and techniques like A* and Dijkstra's algorithm, in addition to sampling-based techniques such as Rapidly-exploring Random Trees (RRT). These algorithms are evaluated based on their efficacy in facilitating collision avoidance and enhancing task completion among several robots. To clearly illustrate the proposed methodologies, we provide a simulation demonstrating how three autonomous robots navigate a grid environment filled with obstacles while avoiding collisions with each other. This simulation showcases the implementation of the A* algorithm for path-finding. Our findings indicate that integrating advanced algorithms with effective communication techniques significantly improves the performance of cooperative path planning systems. This research contributes to the ongoing development of autonomous robotics by providing a framework that combines decentralized communication with real-time path optimization. The insights gained from this study can inform future research and applications in various fields where autonomous robots are deployed.

Keywords: path planning, Collision avoidance, Algorithms.

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1.Introduction

The emergence of autonomous robots has revolutionized multiple sectors, including logistics and search and rescue missions. The necessity for efficient cooperative path planning is crucial as these robots function in shared surroundings. This entails identifying routes for individual robots while also guaranteeing their collaborative functionality without collisions or interference with one another responsibilities.

2.Background

Cooperative path planning is classified into centralized and decentralized methodologies. Centralized systems depend on a singular controller to oversee all robots, but decentralized systems enable robots to make autonomous decisions

based on localized information. Both methodologies possess distinct advantages and limitations, especially concerning scalability and robustness in dynamic environments.

3. Path-planning algorithms

3.1 Graph search algorithm's

Graph search algorithms like A* and Dijkstra's are commonly used for finding optimal paths in static environments. The A* algorithm combines the benefits of Dijkstra's algorithm and a heuristic to guide the search process.

Mathematical Formulation:

The A* algorithm uses the following cost function:

$$f(n) = g(n) + h(n)$$

where:

- $f(n)$ is the total estimated cost of the cheapest solution through node n .
- $g(n)$ is the cost from the start node to node n .
- $h(n)$ is the heuristic estimated cost from node n to the goal.

The heuristic function $h(n)$ can be defined as the Manhattan distance:

$$h(n) = |X_n - X_g| + |Y_n - Y_g|$$

3.2 Sampling-based algorithm's

Sampling-based algorithms, such as Rapidly-exploring Random Trees (RRT), demonstrate efficacy in high-dimensional areas and dynamic environments. RRT incrementally builds a tree by randomly sampling points in the space and connecting them to existing nodes.

Mathematical Formulation:

The RRT algorithm involves:

1. Randomly sampling a point q_{rand}
2. Finding the nearest vertex $Q_{nearest}$ in the tree
3. Extending towards q_{rand} by a distance d

$$q_{new} = q_{nearest} + \frac{|(q_{rand} - q_{nearest})|}{d} * (q_{rand} - q_{nearest})$$

3.3 Swarm Intelligence

Swarm intelligence techniques, such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), can be adapted for cooperative path planning by allowing robots to share information about their paths and adjust their trajectories accordingly.

4. Communication Strategies

Effective communication is crucial for cooperative path planning. Robots must share their positions, planned paths, and any changes in their environment.

- **Leader-Follower Models:** One robot acts as a leader while others follow its path.
- **Decentralized Communication:** Robots exchange information directly with neighboring robots.

5. Simulation Scenario

To illustrate cooperative path planning, we implemented a simulation where three autonomous robots navigate a grid environment with obstacles while avoiding collisions with each other.

5.1 Code implementation

1. we started with defining the Node class that represents each cell in the grid.
2. we defined secondly the heuristic function that calculates the Manhattan distance between two points 'a' and 'b', it's usually used to know how far in the node from the end point
3. after, we implemented the A* algorithm as follow:

```
def a_star(start, goal, grid):
    open_set = PriorityQueue()
    open_set.put(Node(start))
    came_from = {}
    g_score = {start: 0}
    f_score = {start: heuristic(start, goal)}
```

Where:

- open_set: A priority queue that keeps nodes to be evaluated.
 - came_from: A dictionary to rebuild the path once the goal is reached and found.
 - g_score: A dictionary tracking the cost from the start node to each node.
 - f_score: A dictionary tracking the total cost from start to goal passing by each node.
4. Then we created a while loop that continues until there are no nodes left in the open set. It keeps getting the node with the lowest f_score and checks if it is the goal node. If so, it calls reconstruct_path to return the path.
 5. After, we keep iterating over all potential movements (up, down, left, right) to find neighboring nodes. It checks if each neighbor is not an obstacle (represented by a value of 1 in the grid). If valid, it calculates a tentative g_score for that neighbor.
 6. If the new path to a neighbor is better than what was previously recorded or if it's not yet evaluated, it updates:
 - g_score will be replaced with the new cost
 - f_score will contain the new estimated total cost
 then, the neighbor will be added to the open set for further evaluation.
 7. If no path is found after passing by every possible option in the open set, it returns an empty list.
 8. Finally, we define the function reconstruct_path that rebuilds the path starting from the start to the end point by backtracking the came_from dictionary to return it in the exact order:

```
def reconstruct_path(came_from, current):
    total_path = [current]
    while current in came_from:
        current = came_from[current]
        total_path.append(current)
    return total_path[::-1]
```

5.2 Results

This simulation represents the three robots navigating respectively from the starting points to their goal while avoiding obstacles:

- **Nodes:** we got three starting points with three distinct color (green, blue, yellow), end points are represented with the black color
- **Paths:** each path has the color of his staring point
- **Grid representation:** The grid shows obstacles represented by black squares.

6. Conclusion

Cooperative path planning is crucial for the efficient deployment of autonomous robots in intricate situations. By integrating advanced algorithms with effective communication techniques and real-time path changes depending on local variables and robot interactions, we can improve efficiency and safety in multi-robot systems.

7. References

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